

18TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON CHEMISTRY AND THE ENVIRONMENT

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11 – 15 JUNE 2023 VENICE, ITALY

Venue:

SCIENTIFIC CAMPUS

CA' FOSCARI UNIVERSITY OF VENICE (ITALY)

Book of Abstracts

Dear colleagues,

On behalf of the Executive Board of the European Chemical Society, I wish you a warm welcome to this 18th International Conference on Chemistry and the Environment. The European Chemical Society – in short EuChemS – is an overarching society at the European level with over 50 national member societies as members. In this way, EuChemS represents approximately 130,000 chemists from all over Europe. Did you ever realize that by being a member of your national society, you are a member of EuChemS too?

The slogan of this conference is 'Towards a pollution free society', which is well aligned with activities from EuChemS. The European Commission recently set up the Zero Pollution Stakeholder Platform and EuChemS was invited to join. The platform will effectively mainstream the zero pollution agenda by bringing together stakeholders and experts of different policy areas, including health, agriculture, research and innovation, transport, digitalization and the environment. EuChemS will emphasize to address the Zero Pollution challenges from the chemistry perspective in a science-based approach.

I am here in the Netherlands, but you are in the beautiful city of Venice, that I am sure will inspire you to have fruitful and constructive discussions on how to get to zero pollution and how to address many other challenges to create a sustainable environment. I wish you a very enjoyable conference!

Floris Rutjens

President of the European Chemical Society (EuChemS)

Higher Education Modernization-Pharmacist and Environmental Science

N. Milić^{1*}, M. Milanović¹, S. Bijelović², J. Sudji¹, N. Milošević¹

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Hajduk Veljkova 3, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, Futoška 121, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

natasa.milic@mf.uns.ac.rs

There are numerous evidences about the negative effects of environmental contaminants on human health. However, many health-care professionals (i.e. medical doctors, dentists and pharmacists) are not able to comprehend the impact of environment on human health due to the lack of subject related to this topic during bachelor and master education. Therefore, it is of utmost importance to prepare future pharmacists for all the requirements of 21st century making environmental health and protection, a part of their standard curriculum. In Republic of Serbia, pharmacists are educated at four national universities. In spite of that, only at the Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, pharmacy students have possibility to choose as the elective subject "Water Quality in Pharmacy and Balneology". Since 2014, this subject is included in the curriculum at the third year of integrated academic studies in pharmacy. The course aim is acquisition of knowledge in the field of quality, usage, importance and health safety of water for various purposes in the pharmacy and balneology. The course is organized through the combination of theoretical and practical lessons. In addition, students are obligate to write a report regarding the water supply system and the current status of wastewater treatment in their home town. Besides the important topics related to water as a raw material in the pharmaceutical industry and its application in hydrotherapy, water quality is studied from the wider perspective. Particularly, the current priority substances list under the Water Framework Directive and other substances of interest that can be present in raw water (in ng/L concentrations) together with the associated health issues are discussed. Visits to institutions such as Institute of Public Health, the public utility company "Water and Sewerage" and the special hospital for rheumatoid disease that deal with water quality issue from different angles are part of the practical education. Understanding the water quality for various purposes in the pharmacy, pharmaceutical industry and balneology and their importance in the health-care system realizing the close connection between health care and the environment are the expected outcomes of the course. There are numerous opportunities for pharmacy students and pharmacists to slow down ecosystem degradation and improve the status of the environment. The improvement of curriculum through making environmental health a part of the standard education could ensure acquisition of necessary competence for environmentally conscious pharmacy students.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the Provincial Secretariat for Higher Education and Scientific Research, AP Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia [Grant number 142-451- 3120/2022-01].